

Numinous Cliff Mountain Temple (Lingyan shan si 靈岩山寺)

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Numinous Cliff Mountain Temple (Lingyan shan si 靈岩山寺) stands outside the city of Suzhou 蘇州, dominating the waterway that debouches into Lake Tai at Xukouzhen 胥口鎮. This mountain-top site was originally the location of a summer palace, the Guanwa gong 館娃宮 (Lodging Beauties Palace) constructed at vast expense for King Fuchai of Wu 吳王夫差 (r. 495-473 BCE) for his beloved favorite Xi Shi 西施. Xi Shi, one of the four great beauties of ancient China, was presented to the last king of Wu by his greatest enemy, King Goujian of Yue 越王勾踐 (r. 496-465 BCE), to seduce him to his doom. After the fall of Wu in 473 BCE, this great palace was destroyed. The history of the site is obscure until the Eastern Jin dynasty, when Lu Wan 陸玩 (278-341), a member of the distinguished Lu family of Wu Commandery, constructed the first Buddhist temple here. In the Liang dynasty (502-557), the Bodhisattva Zhiji 智積菩薩 (Sanskrit: Pratibhanakuta) is said to have manifested himself here to spread the Buddhist faith. In honor of this, numerous stupas were erected on this site from 503 onwards. In the early Song dynasty, the temple became a Chan Buddhist institution (having previously been a Luzong 律宗 temple), only to be temporarily rededicated as a popular religion foundation honoring Han Shizhong 韓世忠 (1090-1151) at the beginning of the Southern Song dynasty. Han Shizhong had played a key role in the founding of the Southern Song dynasty, as general in command at the battle of Huangtiandang 黃天蕩, during which he held off a massive assault by Jurchen forces for 48 days, allowing the Song court and countless refugees to cross the Yangtze River in safety. Even though the temple soon returned to Chan Buddhist worship, the name of the temple in the Southern Song dynasty still commemorated Han Shizhong, who is buried at the foot of the mountain. The Song dynasty also saw the construction of a magnificent pagoda at the temple. Numinous Cliff Mountain Temple underwent cycles of neglect and restoration throughout the Yuan, Ming, and Qing dynasties, only to suffer almost total destruction during the Taiping Rebellion of 1850-1864. The temple was subsequently rebuilt, but in 1926, it became a Pure Land Buddhist institution, and received its present name in 1932, as chosen by Master Yinguang 印光 (1861-1940). In 1966, at the beginning of the Cultural Revolution, the monastic community was forced to leave, and the buildings were abandoned, but after 1976, restoration began. The temple has officially been active again since 1980 and continues to the present day. In 1990-1991, a program of restoration returned the Song pagoda to its original appearance, and the temple complex remains a popular pilgrimage site as well as receiving the occasional tourist.

Date Range: 494 BCE - 2021 CE

Region: Numinous Cliff Mountain Temple (Lingyan shan si 靈岩山寺)

Region tags: China, Jiangsu Province, Suzhou

The mountain at Lingyan, and surrounding region (Lake Tai).

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Zhang Yiliu 張一留, Suzhou Lingyan shan zhi 蘇州靈巖山志. Suzhou: Lingyan shan si 靈巖山寺, [1947] 1994.
- Source 2: Zhou Hongdu 周鴻度, Lingyan shan 靈巖山. Suzhou: Guwuxian chubanshe 古吳軒出版社, 1998.
- Source 3: Wang Yu 王譽, Song Pingjiang chengfang kao 宋平江城坊考. Nanjing: Jiangsu guji chubanshe, 1999

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://www.szlys.cn/>
- Source 1 Description: This is the official website of Numinous Cliff Temple, providing a detailed account of its modern history.
- Source 2 URL: <https://baike.baidu.com/item/%E7%81%B5%E5%B2%A9%E5%B1%B1%E5%AF%BA/35052>
- Source 2 Description: The Baidu entry on Numinous Cliff Temple gives an overview of the history of the site and quotes some important literature on the subject.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Illicit

Notes: The temple at Numinous Cliff has apparently never been subject to any kind of pre-modern or scientific excavation. However, the tomb of Han Shizhong at the foot of the hill experienced an attempted robbery in the Qing dynasty. According to Zhang Yiliu 張一留, Suzhou Lingyan shan zhi 蘇州靈巖山志, the tomb robber was knocked out by a gust of wind from inside the grave.

Reference: 一留 張. 蘇州靈巖山志. 靈巖山寺.

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1796-1820

Notes: The precise date of this attempted tomb robbery is not recorded, but it is said to have been "early" in the reign of the Jiaqing Emperor.

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: None

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

↳ Type of elevation

– Hill

Notes: Lingyan shan is a hill, the height of which reaches 182 meters above sea level. It is, however, extremely steep, rising from a very low plain.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Water feature

Notes: The temple at Lingyan shan is located at the site of an ancient palace complex, the Guanwa Palace, constructed by King Fuchai of Wu for his beloved consort, Xi Shi. This palace was completely destroyed in 473 BCE, when the kingdom of Wu was conquered. However, the so-called King of Wu's Well (Wuwang jing 吳王井) is supposed to represent one of the only remaining features of the original Guanwa Palace.

Reference: 螿王. 姑蘇志. 上海書局.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: The temple at Lingyan shan is located approximately half way between the city of Suzhou, and where the Xu River debouches into Lake Tai. The siting of this temple is rural, but the spatial relationship with the Xu River gives easy access both to the Lake, the canal complex around this area of Suzhou (including ultimately the Grand Canal), and the internal network of waterways inside Suzhou, which would in antiquity have allowed members of the royal family of Wu and their successors to sail from the citadel at the center of the city to the palace--and later temple--at Numinous Cliff.

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

↳ Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:

– Yes

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: Well

Notes: The only feature of the royal palace that once stood on this site that is supposed to survive is the King of Wu's Well (Wuwang jing 吳王井) which continues to be promoted as a tourist attraction. Although not particularly dramatic, this feature has long been celebrated in poetry.

– Other [specify]: Roadway

Notes: The visit of Emperor Kangxi of the Qing dynasty 清康熙 (r. 1662-1722) to this site in 1689 resulted in the construction of a new access route: the Imperial Way (Yudao 御道). This would result in a permanent change to the landscape of the site. The change is reflected in Emperor Kangxi's poem on the subject "Climbing Numinous Cliff" (Deng Lingyan 登靈岩).

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Reference: Olivia Milburn. *Cherishing Antiquity: The Cultural Construction of an Ancient Chinese Kingdom*. Harvard University Asia Center. isbn: 9780674726680.

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

– Memorial

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– Periodically

Notes: There has been periodic reconstruction of this temple following the destruction of the original Wu palace and the construction of a religious institution on this site. This is part of a regular process of maintenance.

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: Recent reconstructions include the major rebuilding that took place in the reign of the Kangxi Emperor (r. 1661-1722), which were themselves destroyed in warfare in 1860 during the reign of Emperor Xianfeng (r. 1850-1861), and was rebuilt in the reign of his successor, Emperor Tongzhi (r. 1861-1875). Most of the present buildings date to the reconstruction in the 1930s under Master Yinguang 印光法師 (1861-1940), with further work being carried out in 1980-1982 following the Cultural Revolution (when the entire site was abandoned) under the auspices of Master Mingxue 明學法師 (1923-2016) .

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: Since the medieval period, this place has been associated with the Bodhisattva Zhiji, and as such could be understood as used for the worship of a semi-divine human being. Master Yinguang, who established Numinous Cliff Temple as a Pure Land foundation, was believed to be a manifestation of the Bodhisattva.

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

Notes: At the foot of Numinous Cliff stands the complex surrounding the tomb of the Song dynasty general, Han Shizhong (1089-1151). This consists of a memorial hall, spirit road (with tomb guardian figures now destroyed), and the grave site itself. The magnificent huge stele erected at this site features an inscription by Emperor Xiaozong of the Song dynasty 宋孝宗 (r. 1162-1194), with a biography of the deceased in 13,000 characters by Zhao Xiong 趙雄 (1129-1194) in the calligraphy of Zhou Bida 周必大 (1126-1204). This stone was unfortunately cracked by a storm in 1939, and reassembled in its present form in 1946.

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Notes: However, the erection of a traveling palace within the confines of the temple during the Qing dynasty does represent an external financial and material donation.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Notes: The original motives of Lu Wan in presenting his home at Lingyan shan to become a Buddhist foundation are obscure, but it appears to have been a gesture of devotion.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Notes: Although this place was not constructed specifically for housing sacred texts, it is the site today of an important Buddhist library, the Zangjing ge 藏經閣 or Pavilion for Storing Sutras, which contains 47,000 + volumes, including a complete copy of the Qianlong era Longzang 龍藏 tripitaka of 1733.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: The temple at Lingyan shan is located right at the top of the mountain, on the site of

the former Guanwa Palace.

Reference: Olivia Milburn. *Cherishing Antiquity: The Cultural Construction of an Ancient Chinese Kingdom*. Harvard University Asia Center. isbn: 9780674726680.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– I don't know

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– I don't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 414

Notes: The main hall of this temple, the Daxiong baodian 大雄寶殿, has the dimensions 23 x 18 m, and the height to the ceiling is also 18 m.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 34

Notes: The tallest structure on this site is the Duobao fota 多寶佛塔 brick pagoda. A pagoda was first constructed at this temple in 503, but the present structure dates to the Southern Song dynasty, having been constructed in 1147. The original contents of this pagoda were all destroyed in a lightning strike in 1600, but the brick core was undamaged and has been periodically restored since then, most recently a complete external restoration carried out in 1989.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth
– No

↳ Sand
– No

↳ Clay
– No

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: None

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: brick

Notes: According to the *Wumen biaoysin* 吳門表隱, before the present Song dynasty pagoda was built (which has a brick core), there was already a brick pagoda on this site, known as the *Zhuanta* 磚塔, which was constructed by Sun Chengyou 孫承祐 in 977 to commemorate his sister, who had married into the *Qian* 錢 ruling family of the kingdom of *Wu-Yue* 吳越. The location of this earlier tower is unknown.

Reference: 震濤 顧. 吳門表隱.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– I don't know

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: At the entrance to the temple complex, there are figures of the Four Heavenly Kings, 4.5 meters tall. The main hall of the temple features a representation of the Buddha, 6 meters tall, carved in 1897. This represents part of a group of sculptures, along with attendant figures of Mahakasyapa and Ananda.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Animals are depicted in the sculptures and decoration at this temple, but with a strong emphasis on those with some religious significance, e.g. lions.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– I don't know

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– No

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: During its history, the temple and surrounding area has frequently been ornamented with carved calligraphic inscriptions; to give but one example of this, Emperor Hongwu of the Ming dynasty 明洪武 (r. 1368-1398) presented the temple with a tablet in imperial calligraphy reading: "Requiting the Nation Perpetual Blessings Chan Buddhist Temple" (報國永祚禪寺). Alternatively, Emperor Qianlong of the Qing dynasty 清乾隆 (r. 1735-1796) would present the temple with a tablet reading "The Fragrant Forest of the Wu Garden" (吳苑香林); the former highlights the religious significance of this site, the latter highlights its early history as a Wu royal palace.

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: None

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: None

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– I don't know

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

–Secco

Notes: The Baicheng yanshui 百城烟水 records a supernatural story about the paintings in this temple, said to date from the Liang dynasty: "There was a strange monk who entered [the temple] to rest and during the night he painted his portrait on the wall and then left. A foreign monk said: 'This is a portrait of the Bodhisattva Zhiji of the Western lands.'" This was the beginning of the association between Lingyan shan and this Bodhisattva.

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– I don't know

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: None

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: None

↳ Other type of decoration:

– I don't know

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– I don't know

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: Although not initially important as a burial site, the tomb of Han Shizhong is located at the foot of Lingyan Temple, and this was for a time highly important in the development of the temple complex. Partly this was because Han Shizhong was an important donor in his lifetime, his family remained engaged with promoting this site, and also because the temple (though it remained a Buddhist foundation) was temporarily renamed in his honor, first to Han Qiwang gongde si 韓蕲王功德寺 (Han, King of Qi's Successful Virtue Temple) and then to Xianqin chongbao chanyuan 顯親崇報禪院 (Glorifying the Family and Worshipping Reciprocity Chan Buddhist Monastery). Although this second name lacked any specific reference to Han Shizhong, it was still frequently stated at the time that the temple's new name was also chosen to commemorate his achievements.

Reference: 成大 范. 吳郡志. 江蘇古籍出版社.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– No

↳ For the worship of a deified human:

– No

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:

– Yes

Notes: As one of the key figures in the founding of the Southern Song dynasty at a time when large areas of China fell under Jurchen domination, Han Shizhong was certainly regarded by many persons as a hero.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

↳ Significant value:

Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolic value

– Yes

Notes: The tomb of Han Shizhong was robbed in the 18th century, and again in the 1830s. According to the account by Zhang Yiliu 張一留, given in Suzhou Lingyan shan zhi 蘇州靈巖山志: "At the beginning of the Jiaqing Emperor's reign, a robber broke open the tomb. He began by pulling out a brick [from the vault]. Suddenly a cold wind hit him and knocked him over. After a long time, he came to. He picked up a mirror and took it home to show to his wife, [but when he arrived] it was already broken." There are numerous legends of tombs in this area of China throwing things at would-be robbers, so this is quite a common kind of tale.

Reference: 一留 張. 蘇州靈巖山志. 靈巖山寺.

↳ Some value, valuable or useful objects:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: None

↳ Other

– I don't know

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: A number of individuals are buried on the slopes of Numinous Cliff Mountain, and this continues to cause considerable controversy, since this is the site of the grave of Peng Lingzhao 彭令昭 (1932-1968; better known by her pseudonym of Lin Zhao 林昭), who was tortured and executed for treason in 1968. This grave is the focus of annual ceremonies of commemoration by activists, which attract adverse reactions from the authorities.

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– Yes

Notes: Numinous Cliff Temple is the site of burial for senior monks and abbots who have lived and worked in the monastery there, but other burials have also been carried out in the vicinity, sometimes in the context of family groups.

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: None.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: Since Numinous Cliff Temple is a Buddhist foundation, the supreme deity present is the Buddha.

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

–Other [specify]: None

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

Notes: The legends associated with Han Shizhong's tomb suggest that his spirit was believed to be present, and to attack those attempting to disturb his tomb.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:
– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
– Yes

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:
– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:
– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:
– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:
– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:
– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):
– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue visible:
– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:
– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:
– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: The majority of offerings are of food or flowers.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: None

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

- ↳ Is it required:
 - No
- ↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: None

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

- ↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
 - I don't know

Notes: One problem with determining the strictness of pilgrimage is that Numinous Cliff Temple has also been a major tourist attraction since at least the time of the Song dynasty. Descriptions like that given by Zhu Changwen 朱長文 (1041-1100) in his *Wujun tujing xuji* (Further Records of the Illustrated Guide to Wu Commandery) make this quite understandable: "I once climbed the slopes of Numinous Cliff Mountain, looked down upon Lake Tai, and gazed upon the Dongting islands in that vast expanse of water, and at a glance I could see one thousand li. Verdant cliffs and emerald embankments lay like gems between the waves; it really was an exceptionally beautiful vista."

Reference: 長文 朱. 吳郡圖經續集. 江蘇古籍出版社.

- ↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:
 - No
- ↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:
 - No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– Yes

↳ Are these routes maintained together with the place:

– Yes

Notes: Access to the temple is along the Imperial Way (yudao 御道) which was constructed in 1689 on the occasion of a visit by the Kangxi Emperor 清康熙 (r. 1661-1722).

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Yes

↳ Priests

– No

↳ Local elites

– Yes

↳ Private contributions

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: None

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: The wooden communal dining hall is used on these occasions.

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: Festivals occur throughout the year, on a regular schedule.

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: Certainly in the hundreds, if not thousands.

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

Reference: 藝王. 姑蘇志. 上海書局.

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

– Elites

– Non-elites

– Religious professionals

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: thousands of worshippers

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: This site is a Buddhist temple, therefore there are regular services, as well as occasional special ceremonies.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, this temple is under the auspices of the Pure Land Buddhist tradition, and under Master Mingxue 明學 who took charge of Lingyan shan si in 1980, this site has been promoted as a teaching center.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– I don't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

Notes: The temple at Numinous Cliff was originally established during the Jin dynasty, and has repeatedly changed affiliation within the Buddhist faith, being at various times a Luzong, Chan, and Tiantai foundation. At present, since 1926, this has been a Pure Land Buddhist temple.

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– I don't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– No

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– No

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– I don't know

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– Yes

Notes: One of the key texts of Tiantai Buddhism was actually written at this site by the fourth patriarch Zhiyi 智顓 (538-597), the Lotus Samadhi Rite of Repentance (Fahua sanmei 法花三昧).

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– No

Notes: To be precise, the original construction of this place was as a royal palace for the ancient kingdom of Wu, so there is no religious element at that time; and Buddhism was not introduced to China until much later. However, there are later stories concerning the manifestations of a Bodhisattva at this site.

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– No

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